

MODERN METHODS IN DISTANCE LANGUAGE TEACHING OF FOREIGN LANGUAGES

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ABSTRACT: This article is devoted to the analysis of the modern methods in distance language teaching of foreign languages and how these methods have revolutionized the way of learning, providing learners with flexible, accessible, and personalized learning opportunities.

KEYWORDS: distance learning, learning apps, artificial intelligence online courses, language learning.

INTRODUCTION: Technology has transformed the way we learn foreign languages. The traditional classroom setting is no longer the only option, as learners can now access language courses anywhere. In this article, we'll explore the various modern methods of distance language teaching of foreign languages such as online language courses, language learning apps, virtual language exchange programs, blended learning, and artificial intelligence (AI) in language teaching as well as considering how they've changed language learning for the better.

MAIN PART: Today technological advances give a great opportunity to teach students over the world, without considering the commuting issues and simply saving time and energy for traveling to the classroom. Flexible scheduling is another option for students, while the learners can combine their extracurricular activities along with their major study. Online language courses have become increasingly popular in recent years due to the convenience they offer. For example, Duolingo, a language learning platform, offers courses in more than 40 languages and has over 500 million users worldwide. These courses allow learners to learn a foreign language at their own pace and schedule and are usually

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offered by reputable institutions and taught by experienced language instructors. Online language courses provide a wide range of learning resources, including video lessons, interactive exercises, and multimedia materials. For instance, Babbel, another language learning platform, offers courses with audio recordings of native speakers and interactive dialogue simulations. In addition, learners can interact with their instructors and peers through online discussion forums and video conferencing, which fosters a sense of community and support.

Language Learning Apps: Language learning apps have gained significant popularity in recent years, as they offer learners the opportunity to learn a foreign language on the go using their smartphones or tablets. For example, Memrise, a language learning app, offers courses in more than 20 languages and has over 50 million users worldwide. These apps usually provide a variety of learning resources, including vocabulary lists, grammar explanations, and interactive exercises. Language learning apps are designed to be fun and engaging, which helps keep learners motivated. Many apps use gamification techniques, such as rewards and points, which further enhance the learning experience. For instance, the app Drops uses colorful visuals and short sessions to teach vocabulary and grammar in a playful way.

Virtual Language Exchange Programs: Virtual language exchange programs allow learners to connect with native speakers of the language they are learning through online platforms. Through these programs, learners can practice their language skills in a real-life context, receive feedback from native speakers, and improve their pronunciation. For example, Italki, a language learning platform, offers virtual language exchange programs where learners can connect with native speakers for language practice sessions. Virtual language exchange programs offer learners the chance to practice their language skills with native speakers without the need to travel to a foreign country. They can also be more affordable than traditional language immersion programs. For instance, the platform Tandem offers virtual language exchange programs with native speakers for free.

Blended Learning: Blended learning combines traditional classroom teaching with online learning. This method allows learners to learn at their own pace while still having access to face-to-face interaction with their instructor and peers. Blended learning courses typically involve a combination of online learning modules and in-person classes or tutoring sessions. For example, EF

Education First offers blended learning courses in several languages, where learners have access to online resources and in-person classes with experienced language instructors. Blended learning allows for personalized learning. Learners can work at their own pace and focus on areas where they need the most improvement. Blended learning courses can also be more affordable than traditional classroom-based courses, as they eliminate the need for learners to travel to a physical classroom.

Artificial Intelligence (AI) in Language Teaching: The use of artificial intelligence (AI) in language teaching is becoming more common. AI-powered language teaching tools can help learners improve their language skills by providing personalized feedback and targeted practice exercises. These tools can analyze learners' strengths and weaknesses and provide customized learning plans to help them reach their language learning goals. For instance, Lingvist, a language learning platform, uses AI to adapt to learners' individual learning styles and provide personalized content and exercises.

CONCLUSION. Modern methods in distance language teaching of foreign languages have revolutionized language learning. Online language courses, language learning apps, virtual language exchange programs, blended learning, and AI-powered language teaching tools provide learners with a range of options to improve their language skills. These modern methods have made language learning more accessible, convenient, and personalized, enabling more people to learn a foreign language and communicate with the world.

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